

CONSIDERATIONS ON THE CHALLENGES OF PLANNING AND MANAGING GREY SWAN EVENTS

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Abstract

Purpose – analyzing some of the challenges faced by decision makers in planning and managing the effects of grey swan events and proposing a set of recommendations

Methodology/approach - mixed methods - qualitative methods (mainly interviews with planners and decision makers in the areas of defense, security and public sector), the analysis to the existing literature and quantitative methods (a questionnaire).

Findings – some of the challenges identified stem from difficulties related to planning under uncertainty, while others derive from organizational issues and psychological considerations

Research limitations/implications – research limitations have derived from the lack of awareness from the decision makers interviewed of the concept of grey swan events and its implications on the organizations

Practical implications – increasing the awareness of the decision makers on the challenges posed by dealing with grey swan events and the importance of planning and preparedness

Originality/value – the authors propose some recommendations in order to improve the management of grey swan events and to mitigate their effects on the public and private organizations

Key words: *planning, grey swan.*

Introduction

The perception of increased uncertainty in the contemporary world has generated a lack of trust in the benefits of planning and the usefulness of tools such as modelling, in private but especially public sectors. Still, uncertainty does not mean that the world is full of “black swan events”, often, events are part of a system of interconnected factors and there are always warning signs regarding the change in the current environment.

The focus of this paper are the planning/management issues faced in relation to grey swan events by public sector organizations and large private organizations, as medium to small organizations seldom plan for these type of events, due to their limited planning resources (including lack of personnel, tools, time and information).

Are all black swans really black?

The concept of black swan event [Taleb, 2007] is an event with three main attributes: a very low probability of occurring, an extreme impact and impossible to predict in advance. The concept is appealing, but many of the events presented as black swan are at best grey swans, light grey swans, if not downright bleached, almost white swans, to use the same color-related metaphor, as many are not that rare/unpredictable. The 2008 financial crisis was “predicted” by reputable economists [Roubini,2008][Baker,2006][Keen,2007], long before it occurred. The 9/11 events had numerous

precursor signs that were ignored. Brexit was not such a big surprise considering the amount of disinformation, the increased distrust in the British political class, anti-European propaganda fueled by the tabloid media, the rising popularity of the populist and nationalist parties.

Consequently, in today's globalized world, an organization will be more likely confronted with grey swan events, meaning an event that has a low to medium probability of occurring, that may have a big impact on the organization, that can be anticipated if one looks for the precursor signs, which are not taken in consideration by managers/decision makers due to the perceived low probability, despite their potential systemic impact.

Planning related problems deriving from “grey swan events”

Planning and managing grey swan events is difficult even in ideal circumstances, but the task is made even more difficult by a series of specific issues and problems, that shall be discussed in the following section.

The process of planning is not supposed to function as a crystal ball, meant to accurately predict the future before it occurs. Instead, its purpose is to explore potential “alternative realities” in order to help managers make decisions and outline courses of action and their consequences. In this respect, *mathematical models and simulations have sometimes been misunderstood by managers. Instead of considering them a tool to help decision making, there is a tendency to act solely based on a model's outputs, without a proper analysis of all the factors involved and a proper decision making process.* There are unfortunately numerous examples [Sample, 2020] of over-reliance on models/ simulations for public sector decision making.

The problems may derive from improper modelling, but also from the lack of decision makers understanding of what modelling means and from the tendency to politicize decision making, by choosing models that advise a course of action fitting the decision makers' political convictions, interests or values. Lack of time (often deriving improper planning) tempts decision makers to consider modelling as a form of crystal ball that can accurately predict the future and can provide rapid answers, ignoring that models may be based on faulty input data (insufficient or low quality) and assumptions.

Strategic plans are by definition aimed at the achievement of medium/long term results, but this may lead to an over-generalization of their contents and a tendency to focus exclusively on formulating goals and objectives. A common issue derives from the *lack of correlation between the strategic plans and operational plans in terms of level of detail, assigning the responsibilities, the chain of reports, command and authority and the allocation of financial resources.*

Strategic plans are meant to provide the context for the development of operational plans, while they should depend on the inputs from the latter in order to remain realistic. Sometimes managers (especially when constrained by time, lack of personnel or financial resources) tend to underestimate the importance of a good strategic plan and build one that is too generic, while at the same time include in operational plans only on the pressing, short term issues. This has the potential to cause an almost permanent state of perceived emergency, leading to a crisis management (“fire-fighting”) approach even for events that were perfectly foreseeable and plannable.

On the other hand, the operational plans are not the place to clearly identify goals and objectives. When strategic plans are not clear and specific enough, the entire planning process will be flawed. Brilliantly formulated policies, concepts, well-chosen words, positive thinking and good intentions do not make a good foundation for realistic planning. Strategic managers may avoid giving clear directions and making strategic decisions as an attempt to avoid responsibility for difficult decisions and may be tempted to push the problems down the line, towards the operational managers. In turn, the latter may not perform to the best of their abilities faced with a lack of clear and achievable objectives and they may be forced to make decisions under pressure. The result of this permanent shifting of responsibility between strategic planning and operational planning may generate mediocre results at best and serious problems at worst.

The example on how the French authorities dealt with the face masks stocks required by a possible pandemic is representative. France went from a stock of 1 billion surgical masks, 700 million FFP2

masks in 2009 to only 150 million surgical masks and no stocks of FFP2 masks in 2020 [Stanghellini, 2020], based on cost reduction considerations [Delattre, 2015].

There was a clear lack of correlation between the doctrines, strategic plans and the operational plans. The strategic decisions were taken at ministry of health/government level, without clearly establishing the way they were going to be translated into operational plans at the levels of hospitals (especially private ones), without assigning clear responsibilities and authority.

Changes in strategy, with no prior analysis regarding the potential scenarios that may occur, can also hamper effective planning. The reasons this situation occurs are varied: resource scarcity, distrust/lack of understanding from the decision makers related to the importance of such planning tools, ideological considerations that influence decision making and financial reasons. Unfortunately, resources planned for grey-swan events are the first to be cut, as they are perceived as a waste of public money allocated for events that may never happen, as opposed to “real and pressing” issues.

Another issue that may lead to the managerial inability to deal effectively with gray swan events derives from psychological considerations related to the perception that *plans are a static, rigid, time consuming tool, useful perhaps in stable, low uncertainty times, but less suited to rapidly changing environments.*

There is a natural (albeit ineffective) tendency for managers to avoid changes and to stick to already existing plans, as a sort of reassurance that if something happens, they will be prepared. Together with overreliance on models, a rigid approach to planning is a coping mechanism that allows the avoidance of a difficult decision making process and of having to choose a course of action, with its associated risks and opportunity costs.

The “end states” in Lykke’s model [Lykke, 1989] of developing a strategy are often understood by managers as a final destination, when they should be viewed as a set of desirable future conditions that are going to evolve together with the changes in the input data, the environment, the decisions made and even the decision makers themselves. Strategies are just meant to provide a structured framework for measures that need to be taken during the normal functioning of an organization.

Flexible planning does not mean drastic changes in doctrines, strategies and plans without a careful analysis of the environment, potential scenarios and their implications and probabilities. In the case of French mask stocks, the strategy was changed drastically and suddenly, based on short term financial considerations. The probability of a pandemic occurring was the same, the mask requirements for effectively dealing with the effects of the disease were the same, what had changed was the political orientation and the short term financial priorities.

The issue of responsibility is yet another area of potential problems in planning and managing grey swan events. Government officials and CEO’s share the tendency to focus on the present, and to postpone/avoid measures for medium term, especially related to medium or low probability events.

The tendency is enhanced in situations where the decision makers do not keep their position for long and when the accountability is low. This is especially true for the public sector, if decision makers are appointed and then replaced, strategies are not translated into operational plans, measures initiated are not finalized, as each decision maker is more interested in imposing their own vision than continuing to put in practice the previous decision maker’s one. In the public sector, decision makers are inclined to make decisions based on short term considerations, as they are going to be held responsible by their electoral base the latest on the next elections, not after 10 years, when the results of some measures may become visible. Planning experts may come with analyses and recommendations, but they may be overlooked if they don’t fit with the current priorities and it is easy to blame the predecessors for the current problems and decision.

In the private sector, this tendency derives from the need to provide good financial results at the end of the year, so there are few ways of incentivizing managers to prioritize medium term decisions related to low probability grey swan events over short term considerations.

Another important issue related to translating planning into concrete measures derives from the fact that *many strategic plans ignore the financial aspects of implementing the objectives identified*, as these considerations are postponed to the operational planning phase or are dealt with in the annual budget.

Resource planning suffers from inertia and the budgeting process (especially in the public sector) is a lengthy and complicated process that allows limited flexibility for adjustment in case precursors of trouble are identified. Managers have to deal each month with prioritizing scarce resource on short term and giving precedence for urgent, current resource needs compared to allocating resources for hypothetical future events seems like a rational choice.

In the case of French authorities' decision to reduce costs by dismantling the stocks of face masks and assigning the responsibility to keep stocks to the hospitals was based solely on the desire to reduce budgetary expenses, without further analysis on the issue if the hospitals (public and private) have the financial resources to ensure such stocks.

Often decision makers view strategic decisions as separated from their costs implications – after all, they are about the future, and they have to deal with budgets and resources now, in the present. There is a natural tendency to postpone the cost estimations of potential courses of action for the time when they are due to be implemented and included in the annual budgetary plans, or to leave such “details” for the middle-level decision makers. The result is that medium or long term strategic decisions can easily become unrealistic in relation to the resources they require, leading to problems in implementing them fully, when the time comes, as the amount of resources they require each year has not been planned.

Estimating resources for medium to long term is of course a difficult task and the margin of error is significant, but the point of estimating the resource requirements of strategic decisions is not to make a detailed budget for the next 20 years – which of course it would be impossible, or to make a resource driven plan. The purpose should be to give managers a better idea about the financial sustainability of a decision, about the potential implications of the various courses of action, about the benefits and drawbacks of each of them, and to help them make the best decision possible with the information available at that point.

In the public sector especially, with yearly budgetary allocations, managers have little choice in regard to the time-frame for estimating the resource implications of the strategic decisions. The decisions for the next three years have to keep into account the estimated budget envelope for maximum that time-frame, and there is little time, resources or sometimes interest, to make simulations of the financial implications of decisions for a longer time-frame.

The result is that public sector managers often have a narrow, budget driven approach to management, and there is little incentive for them to use planning tools such as planning scenarios, modelling and simulations (with some exceptions such as the military and civil emergency agencies).

Potential solutions for mitigating the impact of planning related problems deriving from “grey swan events

Based on the issues identified above, this section proposes some recommendations in order to improve the management process:

- Clearly defining the responsibilities for the plans development and execution, the reporting process and the evaluation of the results, followed by corrective actions. The more the responsibility is blurred within the organizational structure, the bigger the lack of effectiveness in managing grey swan events.
- Assigning clear accountability for strategic decisions and changes in strategy (from the highest level down to the lower levels), even if the effects of strategic decisions will only become visible after some time.
- Implementing a system of incentives to encourage a medium term approach to management instead of a short term, budget driven one.
- Strategic plans should be financially sustainable, and strategic decisions should not be taken without considering the financial implications. The objectives established should be correlated with the level of available/allocated resources beforehand, in the planning phase, to avoid the situation where the manager is forced to take short term actions to free those resources from other activities, after the budget is approved.

- Multi-annual resource planning can help managers be aware of the implications in time of various decisions (from financial implications to the number of required personnel, the investment requirements, the operating and maintenance requirements etc) and of the life cycle costs involved by specific courses of action.
- Strategic decisions should be based on cost-benefit analysis of various courses of action, to allow decision makers to be aware of other possible solutions and to understand in more detail the possible systemic and longer term implications of their decisions.
- Using planning scenarios and other similar planning tools to help decision making, including Artificial Intelligence. A better understanding of the meaning of grey swan events, probability, role of modeling, simulation is required for effectively mitigating the effects of grey swan effects.
- Greater flexibility in changing and adapting plans to the current realities, as grey swans do not come un-announced. There usually are clear warning signs, but they are often easy to ignore if complacency sets in regarding the existing plans (considered too good to change). Should plans be viewed as static and rigid and should the managers be reluctant to change them until the schedule time for a new plan, grey swan events may not wait that long and may be perceived as black swans, with huge effects on the organization.
- Integrated planning throughout the organization and the correlation of plans between different levels of the organization (from the ministry/headquarter level down to the component units) and between agencies (for the public sector), including the resource area.
- An honest assessment and acknowledgment of the various organizational factors and individual psychological biases that may increase the likelihood of faulty decisions and judgement errors.
- Applying the concept of lessons-identified and lessons-learned. The analysis of past situations and problems can provide useful insights into problems and how they could potentially be solved, that should be translating into Standard Operating Procedures, protocols and regulations, set up in advance, to be activated when a particular scenario becomes reality. They should be understood, accepted and implemented throughout the organization, following a top down approach (from the strategic planning department/ministry down the hierarchy chain), but should be developed following a bottom up approach, by taking advantage of the inputs (experiences, the problems identified and the solutions found) at all levels of the organization.

Conclusions

In today's globalized environment, that fact that grey swan events can be anticipated if warning signals are heeded, does not mean their effects are not serious or that dealing with them is easy. An effective response to grey swan events requires a complex combinations of factors and measures that should be taken, but the first step is recognizing the need to plan for such events. Even though the probability of a grey swan event is not very high, managers from both public and private organizations should take the necessary steps to plan for them in advance, as dealing with their effects when they happen entails high costs.

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